

Utilizing Complexity Metrics During Code Reviews to Promote Software Sustainability

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Abstract—Software sustainability is critical for Computational Science and Engineering (CSE) software. Highly complex code makes software more difficult to maintain and less sustainable. Code reviews are a valuable part of the software development lifecycle and can be executed to manage complexity and promote sustainability. We have developed a technique to guide the code review process that considers cyclomatic complexity levels and changes during code reviews. Using real-world examples, this paper analyzes metrics gathered via GitHub Actions for several pull requests and demonstrates the application of this approach in support of software maintainability and sustainability.

Index Terms—software sustainability, cyclomatic complexity, software metrics, code review

I. INTRODUCTION

Software sustainability is critical in the Computational Science and Engineering (CSE) domain [1]. While there is no universally agreed upon definition of software sustainability, the proposal for the Software Sustainability Institute [2] said that software sustainability is the “capacity of the software to endure”. Sehestedt, et al. define software sustainability as “cost efficient maintainability and evolvability” [3]. These definitions are both useful in understanding the context of our research.

CSE software projects often begin as a research activity. Software engineering principles are secondary to the research objectives driving the project [4] as good software engineering practices, such as testing, documentation, and design, are often seen as slowing down the progress of the research. Projects developed without sustainability in mind eventually become fragile, sometimes to the point that developers are reluctant to change the code for fear of breaking it.

Code reviews are widely recognized as an important part of a strong verification and validation process [5]–[7]. One way to maintain and even improve software sustainability is

*This paper describes objective technical results and analysis. Any subjective views or opinions that might be expressed in the paper do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Department of Energy or the United States Government.

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through code reviews. However, simply adding code reviews to the software development workflows for a project does not guarantee success. Many projects fail to implement an effective code review process [8]. Poorly reviewed code leads to decreased software quality [9]. The thoroughness and quality of code reviews are often inadequate for code projects in the CSE domain. Poorly performed code reviews lead to less readable and understandable code, which increases the maintenance burden [10].

Prior research lists several software sustainability attributes: extensibility, interoperability, maintainability, portability, reusability, scalability, and usability [11]. A complex code base is detrimental to software maintainability [12] and sustainability. While cyclomatic complexity does not capture all aspects of maintainability, by definition, it does reflect the number of paths through the code, which impacts testability and understandability. Increasing cyclomatic complexity can increase maintenance. While sometimes complex code is necessary, for example, in a performance-critical part of a CSE code, it should, at a minimum, be well-designed and documented. In other words, it is essential to actively manage, not simply limit code complexity.

This paper reports complexity metrics from 14 real-world pull requests (PRs) selected from 2 real-world CSE projects. (GitLab uses the term merge request instead of pull request, but we use pull request or PR throughout the paper for simplicity.) The PRs are of different sizes and types and impact and create varying amounts of complexity. The paper presents an approach for utilizing complexity metrics to guide the code review process in support of software sustainability.

In our prior work, [13], we discussed a variety of metrics in the context of software sustainability, including different measures of size, the number of contributors, complexity, and the Metrix++ maintenance index, which is calculated based on the size and complexity of the code base.

By sampling multiple metrics for a single code base over time, practitioners can glean whether it is becoming more or less sustainable. Such information may help assess the effectiveness of changing development practices or tools. For example, a decreasing maintenance index for a code base following the adoption of a new development practice supports the hypothesis that the new practice is beneficial. That said,

it is never appropriate to make broad conclusions based on a single metric, for example to claim that one code is more sustainable than another.

In follow-up work, we introduced an approach for utilizing complexity data to assist developers in performing code reviews and inform project teams about longer-term changes in sustainability and maintainability from the perspective of cyclomatic complexity [14]. We used the hotspot feature from Metrix++ version 1.7.0 (<https://metrixplusplus.github.io/metrixplusplus/>) to identify complex regions of code based on thresholds and to determine whether or not changes in a pull request add to the complexity of regions above a given threshold.

These metrics can be used to guide and improve PR review efforts. The data can be used, for example, to identify regions of code that should be refactored while working on surrounding code, and support requests that PRs be broken into smaller pieces. The metrics can also be used for monitoring changes in complexity over time, and for helping identify individual developers who might benefit from training in code design. The primary limitations of this work was in the small number of pull requests studied, and in the selection of complexity thresholds.

We have extended our previous work to address those primary limitations. Specifically, we added 10 additional pull requests to our analysis to include a wider variety of sizes and types. Second, we modified how we selected complexity thresholds to increase the relevance of the metrics. The remainder of the paper outlines our research approach, and presents the results along with a discussion of those results, before presenting conclusions and future work.

II. RESEARCH APPROACH AND EXPERIMENT DESIGN

For each of the 14 pull requests we gathered the following metrics: First was the number of lines added and deleted by the pull request, as provided by GitHub and GitLab. (Note that a modified code line counts as one line added and one deleted.) Second, for each of the chosen thresholds, we used the Metrix++ hotspot feature to measure

- The number of regions of code throughout the project “touched” (modified) by the pull request with a complexity equal to or greater than the threshold value after the PR is applied.
- The number of touched regions of code with a complexity equal to or greater than the threshold value after the PR is applied for which the value had an increasing “trend” (increased) due to the changes in the pull request.

After generating database files for the git SHAs denoting the state of the code before and after each pull request, the data for the “touched” metric was gathered using commands of the form:

```
metrix++ limit \  
--db-file=proj1.after.complex.db \  
--db-file-prev=proj1.before.complex.db \  
--max-limit=\
```

```
std.code.complexity:cyclomatic:50 \  
--warn-mode=touched
```

The “trend” metric was gathered by changing the warn-mode option in the above command to “trend” instead of “touched.” Both commands require the specification of a database file based on the previous state of the code (using `--db-file-prev`) and the state of the code after applying the PR (using `--db-file`).

The data collection was semi-automated using a custom GitHub Action that was attached to pull requests made against forks of the primary project repositories. Pull requests were manually copied to the fork, and then the GitHub Action ran against the pull request. If the GitHub Action were to be set up on the primary source code repositories, the collection could have been fully automated. Therefore any project that would choose to adopt this approach could fully automate the metric collection.

A. Choosing Pull Requests

Our previous metric collection activity included only four pull requests, two for each of two open-source scientific software projects. The selection of ten additional PRs, five from each of the two projects, was not random. Rather, we intentionally chose PRs not only of different sizes but also some that mostly added new code and some that mostly modified existing code.

Below is a brief description of the two software projects chosen for our metric collection activity. These are important and long-established projects that are part of the xSDK (<https://xsdk.info/>) and the US DOE Exascale Computing Project Software Technology Focus Area [15]. The project names have been changed to guard against unintended conclusions concerning the sustainability of any specific project.

Project 1 includes linear and non-linear solvers and preconditioners for partial differential equation-based systems of equations. Project 1 is written primarily in C and contains more than 800,000 lines.

Project 2 is a collection of solvers and enabling technologies used for large-scale, complex multi-physics engineering and scientific problems. Project 2 is written primarily in C++ and contains over 4,000,000 lines.

B. Choosing Thresholds

Previously we chose thresholds on a per-project basis, based on the average complexity of the code regions in each project. (Metrix++ code regions include classes, functions, structs, namespaces, etc.) While we still believe that each team should choose custom thresholds that make sense for their project, and those thresholds may correlate with the typical amount of complexity in the code base (so as to not flag too many or too few regions of interest to be useful), for this activity we have chosen fixed default thresholds for two primary reasons.

First, and most important, different levels of complexity within a code base signify different types of concerns about that region of code. Specifically, regions with a cyclomatic complexity of ten or less are commonly considered reasonable

[16], in terms of both testability and the structure of the code. At a cyclomatic complexity around 20-30, concerns increase, until around 50, at which point the code is considered untestable. Sustainability is the core concern of this research, and testability is a necessary condition of sustainability. Finally, cyclomatic complexities greater than 75 indicate a high risk of a “bad fix” [17]. A bad fix is one where fixing a defect introduces one or more additional defects. Considering the definition of cyclomatic complexity, it is not surprising that changing a region of code with a cyclomatic complexity of greater than 75 may result in a bad fix. It would be difficult to thoroughly test all possible code paths.

When considering complexity there is the additional concern that goes beyond testability to how well the code is actually tested. The quality of test suites (including line, branch, and statement coverage, for example) for CSE software varies dramatically and must be taken into consideration. For any level of complexity, code that is more poorly tested is a higher concern than code that is better tested. The highest levels of complexity are concerning even for code with significant testing.

Based on this improved understanding of the significance of different complexity thresholds, the single-digit cyclomatic complexity thresholds used in our previous metric gathering activity were removed because regions of cyclomatic complexity less than 10 are not concerning specifically for their level of cyclomatic complexity. While it is possible that unnecessary complexity has been introduced into a region that is still relatively low complexity, that can be said of a region of any non-trivial complexity, and at least regions of complexity below the lowest threshold remain relatively understandable and testable.

We concluded then that it makes more sense to start from established norms for complexity thresholds and adapt if necessary for project or institutional preferences than it does to start from relative thresholds and adapt those. For that reason, cyclomatic complexity was measured with threshold levels of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 75, and 80. These were chosen based on the levels discussed above so we could monitor the behavior of the metrics at and near those levels. We included a subset of these thresholds corresponding closely to the above discussion in our results section.

The second reason for choosing fixed thresholds was to allow our GitHub Action to be both general purpose, and usable out-of-the-box. The GitHub Action uses default values that are suitable for use with any code base and are not project-specific. A project team may still want to customize the threshold values or number of thresholds, and that is both encouraged and easy to do, but no custom configuration is required to get started.

III. RESULTS

Table I contains results for the fourteen chosen pull requests. The data can be understood as follows. The first column lists the number of the pull request (PR), 1-14, within the data set. The second column displays if the PR is from project

1 or project 2 (Proj). The third column lists the number of lines added or modified by the PR. The fourth column lists the number of lines removed or modified by the PR. The last 12 columns display the complexity metrics gathered using Metrix++. Each column is associated with one of six complexity thresholds, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, or 75. The odd numbered columns denote the number of regions above the associated threshold for which the PR modifies or “touches” (To) the code region. The even numbered columns denote the number of regions above the associated threshold for which the PR increases the complexity of the region, which uses the Metrix++ trend (Tr) option.

Figure 1 is a screenshot from the output of the Metrix++ GitHub Action for one of the 14 PRs. The key elements of this output include the Region name, which has been partially hidden to avoid associating the output with a specific code project, the level of complexity of the region (Metric value), the increase in complexity due to the PR (Change trend), and the complexity threshold (Limit). The error code corresponds to the number of regions of code exceeding the specified limit. The GitHub Action is not configured to error out for this kind of error, but that is configurable.

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

In analyzing Table I, there are a few fundamental things to consider. First is the size and type or nature of each PR. Both the size and type of pull request will impact how difficult it is to review the PR. This information is found in the number of lines added or modified and removed or modified, which is available from GitLab or GitHub. Exactly what constitutes a large or small pull request will vary somewhat from project to project. For this analysis, PRs involving a few hundred lines are small, several hundred are medium size, and over a thousand are large.

The type of pull request also has an impact. For example, a pull request might primarily add additional lines to the code base, or it might modify existing code. PR 12 only adds lines of code, while PR 3 mostly modifies lines of code (recall that both the Added and Removed columns include modified lines of code). While it is possible this could indicate that an entirely new section of code was added and another was completely removed, it most often means that a lot of code was modified. If that is not the case, it would be immediately obvious when beginning the review.

The second consideration when analyzing the results in Table I is the amount of complexity added by the PR. Simpler implementations should be considered for changes that would introduce significant complexity. The data does not capture all of the complexity added by the PR. Specifically we are interested in identifying only code regions made more complex by the PR that also have cyclomatic complexity greater than 10. This information is available in the columns with the headings that include “Tr”, which indicates that the complexity of the region is above the listed threshold and also trending upward.

TABLE I
HOTSPOT COMPLEXITY DATA

PR	Proj	Added	Removed	10 To	10 Tr	20 To	20 Tr	30 To	30 Tr	40 To	40 Tr	50 To	50 Tr	75 To	75 Tr
1	1	112	40	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
2	1	5279	448	20	15	11	8	7	4	4	2	4	2	1	0
3	1	332	299	7	0	3	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
4	1	383	37	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	1	387	94	5	3	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	0	0
6	1	15,220	14,875	1959	1	802	0	390	0	231	0	151	0	58	0
7	1	5336	424	6	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
8	2	8	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	2	1339	668	26	7	5	2	3	1	2	1	1	1	0	0
10	2	350	94	4	2	4	2	3	2	3	2	1	1	0	0
11	2	508	3	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	2	642	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	2	977	24	2	1	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	2	245	197	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

```

Run Metrix++
succeeded on Mar 7 in 1m 33s

10 plus complexity regions trending up 0s
28 Metric name : std.code.complexity:cyclomatic
29 Region name : P...p_B...KOS
30 Metric value : 35
31 Modified : True
32 Change trend : +20
33 Limit : 10.0
34 Suppressed : False
35
36 ./:: info: 3 regions exceeded the limit
   'std.code.complexity:cyclomatic' > 10.0 [applied to 'any'
   region type(s)]
37
38 Error: Process completed with exit code 3.

```

Fig. 1. Metrix++ GitHub Action Output

The third consideration is the amount of complexity impacted by the PR. Here we include situations where there is significant complexity in the code region being modified, even if the PR does not increase the complexity. Consider a region of code with cyclomatic complexity of 80 and a PR reduces the complexity of the region to 76. While the complexity of the code region actually decreased, there is still risk associated with complexity in this region. As stated above, complexities greater than 75 are indicative of significant risk of bugs being introduced when new changes are made. In this way, code complexity is a consideration even if a PR does not introduce new complexity.

Existing complexity is measured by identifying the code

regions with cyclomatic complexity greater than 10 after the PR is applied. This information is available in the columns with the headings that include “To”, which indicates that the complexity of the region is above the listed threshold and was “touched” or modified by the PR. For a given threshold, the touched value will always be greater than or equal to the trend value because touched includes regions where the complexity is trending upward, but also those that are trending downward or staying the same. Next, we will examine the 14 PRs more specifically.

A. Low Complexity Pull Requests

Of the 14 PRs, PRs 8, 12, and 14 have zero regions of complexity greater than 10 modified by the PR (touched or

trending up). In other words, no regions are flagged for special consideration. PR 8 is a very small PR touching fewer than a dozen lines. PRs 12 and 14 are of medium size. PR 12 exclusively adds new code, while PR 14 primarily modifies existing code. The data confirms that the PRs in this group not only do not add significant complexity, but importantly also do not modify a high complexity region of code. Even a small change to a complex region of code can be a risk in terms of potential new defects. While the PRs should be reviewed, from a complexity standpoint there are not any code regions with complexity that meet even the lowest threshold to consider during the review. This is particularly interesting when considering that PRs 12 and 14 impact several hundred lines of code.

B. Medium Complexity Pull Requests

PRs 4 and 11 are of a similar and reasonable size. Each has one region of complexity greater than 10, but not greater than 30. This is a range of elevated complexity, but isn't considered untestable. The PRs are different in that PR 4 simply touches its region of moderate complexity, while PR 11 adds to the complexity of its region. In both cases, from the perspective of a code reviewer, the response to the complexity data would be similar. For PR 4, the reviewer might consider if there are testing gaps related to the change or if the code region could be refactored to reduce complexity. For PR 11, the reviewer would additionally consider how the new changes could be implemented with lower complexity.

PRs 3, 7, and 13 have 1-3 regions of complexity greater than 30, but not greater than 50. The complexity of this group is higher than the last, but not to the point of being deemed untestable. PR 3 is of reasonable size and mostly modifies existing code. PR 13 involves nearly 1000 lines, which can be challenging to review thoroughly. PR 7 impacts over 5000 lines of code, which is quite large for a single review. PRs 7 and 13 primarily add new code. PR 3 touches three regions with complexity greater than 30 and one greater than 40. This requires reviewer attention to multiple regions of escalating complexity concern. However, the PR is not increasing the complexity of any of these regions. PRs 7 and 13 have similar levels of complexity concerns, but also increase the complexity of one or more region with complexity greater than 20.

For each PR in this group the number of regions above the 30 threshold is only 1-3. However, PR 3 touches 7 regions with complexity greater than 10 and PR 7 touches 6, while adding complexity to four of those regions. Code regions meeting the higher complexity threshold are more concerning from a complexity standpoint than the lower thresholds, but the lower thresholds, and the rest of the PR for that matter, should not be forgotten. The approach is simply meant to help reviewers prioritize where to spend time, and ensure that regions of higher complexity are not missed.

C. High Complexity Pull Requests

PRs 1, 5, 9, and 10 each increase the complexity of one region of code with a complexity greater than 50. This is the threshold above which the code may be untestable. These regions deserve high scrutiny, and refactoring should be considered. All four PRs also have at least one other region with complexity greater than 10 to review. The PRs in this group vary significantly in size, from less than 200 lines to over 2000 lines. The smallest, PR 1, touches only two regions of code with complexity greater than 10, while the largest, PR 9, touches 26. There are a number of size and complexity considerations for reviewing PR 9. If practical, it may be better to submit PR 9 as a series of smaller changes, or review the commits that comprise PR 9 separately. It is also worth noting that PRs 5 and 9 both increase the complexity of one code region with complexity greater than 70, but not greater than 75, which is the threshold for the final group.

PR 6 is the largest of the 14, and PR 2 is the 3rd largest. These are the only two pull requests that touch regions of code with complexity greater than 75. This level of complexity corresponds to a significant risk of a bad fix. PR 6 is likely too large to review thoroughly. Using these metrics will help address the most significant complexity concerns. Minimally, the data provides a better idea of the complexity that is being added (which for PR 6 is surprisingly little), as well as how many regions of high complexity are impacted, which helps quantify the risk of injecting defects.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We analyzed pull requests from two representative code projects that are part of the xSDK and the US DOE Exascale Computing Project. While our focus is on CSE software, the analysis can be generalized beyond the CSE domain as the data simply reflects the level of existing and new complexity after applying a pull request and is not specific to the CSE domain in any way. The metrics for our analysis were gathered using a GitHub Action developed for this research and can be used by other practitioners and researchers alike.

Highly complex code makes software more difficult to maintain, and less sustainable. However, writing complex code is sometimes necessary due to feature or performance requirements. For these reasons, it is essential to manage complexity, not simply limit it. This paper demonstrates a novel approach to using complexity metrics during code reviews. Specifically, the metrics presented in the paper can be used to localize and reduce complexity. Alternatively, where complex code is needed, a reviewer can use the metrics to ensure that the complex regions of code are understandable, either through a clear design, comments, or a combination of both. This may be particularly helpful for larger PRs. It is essential to be aware of when changes are being made to complex code regions, even if the changes are not increasing complexity, as this can impact the level of confidence tests provide, as well as the risk of injecting new defects. By utilizing complexity metrics during code reviews, a code team can positively impact the sustainability of their project.

In the future, it would be simple to modify our GitHub Action to fail on a region of complexity above a given threshold, which would allow code projects that utilize pre-push testing to apply strict complexity limits to their code. However, this may be difficult to get into production if there are existing regions of code with complexity above the chosen threshold. Another area of possible future work would be to study if the metrics we are gathering could accurately predict where code reviewers made comments on or changes to PRs based on actual PRs that were modified or commented on. A final possible direction for future work would be to apply the metric-gathering process to a CSE software project and gather feedback on its usefulness.

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